

Universe Packet Density – Distinct Universe Packets – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the new 8T in the second representation, i.e. universe packet, two options will be presented. The first is an infinite packet of stationary Lorentz manifolds. That is the option we assumed correct up to now in the 8T thesis. The second option is a limit imposed by nature, which defines a maximal density of manifolds in the packet. This version than implies infinite packets, when limit is reached the newborn manifold is propagating outward from the packet, that seems to agree with time invariant acceleration from areas of extremum curvatures, if the number is ever increasing within one infinite packet, the negative time invariant acceleration should be increasing as well.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line, which is the spin representation.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. Up to this day, we assumed that there is only one packet of stationary Lorentz manifolds, which grow in number. Each manifold has a distinct arrow of time, which is a unique moment of singularity or a unique age. The older the universe the flatter it should be, as it was a subject of pressure from other manifolds for longer temporal periods. That is currently the only option presented in the 8T thesis. However, it now becomes evident that it could be wrong. There could be a limitation of the number of stationary manifolds that composes the packet. Such that if that limit is reached, any metric tensor fluctuations volatile enough will ignite a manifold, which will join a distinct packet. Similar to wave packets, which come in an infinite number. As far as one can see, the current equations of the 8T indicate that the universe has a "sphere packing" structure, an unknown number of thin layers stacked or compressed together in a packet.

If the number is infinite then we have one packet of stationary manifolds. If there exist a limit, there are multiple. Another interesting point, if the number of manifolds in the packet is finite, then the degree of acceleration outward from areas of extremum curvatures is also finite, which is what we required for a stationary manifold. If the number of manifolds increases without a density limit, then the outward acceleration should increase overtime, as more stationary manifolds are in the packet. That seems more correct as we know that the so-called "dark energy" is time invariant. Therefore, that could imply that there is a limitation of density in the packet. We can define this density limit by varying the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{n < K} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2A)$$

$$K \in \mathbb{R}$$

We can parameterize the manifolds presented in (2.1) to put the idea of stationary manifold packets, which are distinct in rigor.

$$s_1 + \sum_{n=2}^{n < K} s_n = Y_1 \quad (2)$$

Moreover, the new structure of the multiverse is the summation of all the universe packets:

$$Y_1 + \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} Y_i = \vartheta \quad (3)$$

In the 8T we assumed there is just one infinite packet, and the dark energy could be an adiabatic variant, which varies very slowly. This paper analyzed the structure of the multiverse by imposing a limitation on the density of the packet, leading to infinite number of distinct packets as described by equations (2) and (3).

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)